

New Composite Materials with a Carbon-Titanium Carbide Hybrid Matrix for High Temperature Applications

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ABSTRACT

2D-composites made of carbon fabrics and C/TiC hybrid matrix are obtained by CVI of TiC within the open pores of 2D-C-C preforms, from $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$ mixtures. Their Young moduli and strength increase with increasing volume fraction of TiC. In compression, failure occurs by interlayer delamination for low v_{TiC} and across the fabric layer for high v_{TiC} . TiC-infiltration lowers the mechanical and thermal anisotropy of the initial 2D-C-C preforms. The new 2D-C-C/TiC composites have a good oxidation resistance up to about 900°C in air. At higher temperatures, a non-protective TiO_2 -layer is formed with an evolution of carbon oxides.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon composites (C-C-composites) are nowadays commonly used in the space industry, as well as, in several other fields (disk brakes, prostheses, etc...). Despite their numerous advantages, they exhibit a few important drawbacks, such as a very poor oxidation resistance (even at temperatures as low as 500-600°C) limiting their applications to non-oxidizing atmospheres.

Such a drawback could be overcome by replacing partly (or even completely) the C matrix by a refractory material fulfilling two conditions: (1) a good chemical compatibility with carbon and (2) a high oxidation resistance; SiC can be such a material. C-SiC composites, obtained by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) of porous C fiber preforms, were found to exhibit higher mechanical strength and modulus than the related C-C composites and their resistance towards air-oxidation remains good up to about 1500°C [1-5].

The use of C-SiC composites is however limited in temperature by the volatility of the SiO_2 -protective layer and thermal decomposition of SiC. Since TiC has a higher thermal stability than SiC, the authors have developed a new family of composites made of a porous C-C fiber preform densified with TiC according to a CVI process. A higher thermal stability, equivalent mechanical strength and modulus, but a somewhat lower resistance towards air-oxidation could be expected, as compared to the C-C/SiC related materials [6-10]. These new C-C/TiC composites could be potential candidates for high temperature structural applications (e.g., TiC is one of the materials that could be used as a first wall in nuclear fusion reactors) [11].

The present contribution gives a general presentation of the 2D-C-C/TiC composites belonging to this family. More detailed studies will be published elsewhere [12,13].

1 - SYNTHESIS

The materials (about 100 samples) were obtained by CVI of TiC within the open pores of 2D-C-C preforms, according to a two step procedure. The preforms were made of a stack of carbon fabrics (woven from PAN or rayon based fibers), thus giving to the related 2D-C-C/TiC composites a two-dimensional microstructure.

In a first CVI-step, the dry preforms were predensified with pyrocarbon (pyrolysis of CH_4), in order to achieve an overall carbon volume fraction of $V_c = 0.40$ to 0.75 . These 2D-C-C preforms are, therefore, characterized by a residual porosity of the order of $V_{pc} = 0.25-0.60$, mainly consisting of open pores of $10-40 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter located either within or between the fabric layers.

In the second and most important step, TiC was deposited, in the pores of the 2D-C-C preforms utilizing a $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$ mixture. The CVI-conditions have been established on the basis of a thermodynamic and experimental approach [6,9,12].

1.1 Thermodynamic approach of the chemical vapor deposition of TiC

Deposition of TiC from $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$ proceeds according the overall equation:

the deposit being made of either pure TiC or of TiC+C (or even TiC+Ti) mixtures depending on the experimental parameters. Furthermore, different by-products appear in the vapor phase.

In order to establish the chemical composition of both the deposit and the vapor phase, it was assumed, in a first step, that states close to equilibrium were actually reached in the CVI-chamber. Thus, a thermodynamic approach could be applied. Such an approach gives for a given temperature, total pressure and initial gas composition, the nature and amounts of the chemical species x present at equilibrium from which thermodynamic yields η_x can be derived according to equations of the types:

$$\eta_{\text{TiC}}(\%) = 100 \frac{\langle \text{TiC}_{\text{eq.}} \rangle}{|\text{TiCl}_4 \text{ in.}|} \quad \eta_{\text{C}}(\%) = 100 \frac{\langle \text{C}_{\text{eq.}} \rangle}{|\text{CH}_4 \text{ in.}|}$$

$|$ and $\langle \rangle$ being, respectively, mole numbers of gaseous or condensed species at equilibrium (eq.) or in the initial composition (in.).

Under the conditions considered here, the thermodynamic calculations lead to the following conclusions:

- the chemical species present at equilibrium in significant amounts are: TiCl_4 , TiCl_3 , TiCl_2 , CH_4 , HCl , H_2 for the vapor phase and TiC,C for the deposit,
- initial compositions free from H_2 ($\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4$ mixtures) lead to TiC deposits that always contain free carbon,
- for a given T,p, $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$ mixtures result in deposits made of either pure TiC or TiC+C mixtures depending on initial compositions, as shown in fig.1 and in agreement with the conclusions of earlier investigators [14,15].
- initial compositions that lead to pure TiC deposits strongly depend on both T and p,
- at rather low temperatures (e.g. 1200 K) and for initial compositions resulting in pure TiC deposits (α close to α_c), an important amount of TiCl_4 remains unreacted at equilibrium and, at the same time, a large quantity of TiCl_3 by-product is formed ($\eta_{\text{TiCl}_4} + \eta_{\text{TiCl}_3} = 73\%$). Thus the TiC thermodynamic yield is low ($\sim 27\%$) (Fig.2).

1.2 Experimental optimization

The thermodynamic approach of complex CVD reaction must be followed by an experimental optimization since it does not take into account such important phenomena as mass transport through boundary layers or surface kinetics. This is particularly true for the CVI of porous substrates (i.e. in-depth deposition) which is known to require conditions quite different from those usually reported for CVD-overcoating (i.e. deposition limited to the external surface of the substrate) [1,2,5,9,12].

The experimental optimization, as well as the synthesis of all the samples tested were performed with a LP-CVD apparatus equipped with a *hot wall* infiltration chamber schematically shown in fig.3. All experiments were run with $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$ gas mixtures characterized by an α ratio close to α_c .

From the analysis of titanium distribution profiles (X-ray electron microprobe analysis), it appeared that the CVD-parameters had to be significantly lowered in order to favor the in-depth pore infiltration with respect to the overcoating of the samples.

Lowering both T (to about $900 < T < 1000^\circ\text{C}$) and D (to about $1 < D < 21$ per hour for a laboratory scale CVI chamber) reduces the reaction rate and increases the lifetime of the reactant molecules diffusing in the pores. In the same manner, decreasing p (to about $0.05 < p < 0.5$ atm.) lengthens their mean free path. Under such conditions, the reactant molecules are allowed to diffuse within the pores before reacting and an in-depth TiC deposition occurs within the whole preforms.

As illustrated in fig.4, the weight increase of the initial 2D-C-C preform progressively slows down as the pores are being filled with TiC, CVI becoming more and more difficult as the pore diameter decreases. However, an almost complete densification can be achieved (residual porosity of a few percents) although it requires long periods (500 hours for laboratory scale samples). As predicted by the thermodynamic calculations, an important amount of both unreacted TiCl_4 and TiCl_3 by-product was observed and had to be eliminated.

2 - MICROSTRUCTURE OF 2D-C-C/TiC COMPOSITES

The 2D-C-C/TiC composites have a 2D microstructure. During the CVI-process TiC is first deposited on the initial pyrocarbon matrix. Later on, it progressively fills the available open porosity, the pore spectrum being shifted towards the small diameter pore side, as shown in fig. 5 and 6. Usually, an *overall* residual porosity V_p of a few percents is observed which is responsible for a weak density gradient from the core (where porosity is high) to the surface, as already found for the 2D-C-C or 2D-C-C/SiC related materials [2,3].

Microprobe analysis has shown that TiC deposited within the pores (α close to α_c) is almost *stoichiometric* (Ti%: $80.3 \pm 0.5\%$; C%: 19.7 (by difference), vs. Ti%: 79.95 and C%: 20.05 in stoichiometric TiC) [16]. As expected from the Ti-C phase diagram, the TiC matrix has an excellent chemical compatibility with the pyrocarbon matrix (no interface reaction). On the other hand, *microcracking* was observed within the TiC-matrix, possibly due to a thermal expansion mismatch between TiC and pyrocarbon (Fig.5).

The properties of the 2D-C-C/TiC were studied, as a function of TiC volume fraction, V_{TiC} , on a series of samples obtained from the same 2D-C-C preforms (characterized by an initial porosity V_{p_0}). In a given series of specimens, the overall volume fraction of carbon V_C (fibers and pyrocarbon matrix) is almost constant, V_{TiC} and V_p being related to one another by:

$$V_C + V_{\text{TiC}} + V_p = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$V_{\text{TiC}} + V_p = 1 - V_C = V_{p_0} \text{ constant} \quad (3)$$

As a result, progressively increasing V_{TiC} leads to a decreasing V_p . Furthermore, in a given series of samples, the highest V_{TiC} value which can be achieved is equal to V_{p_0} (with $V_{p_0} = 0.25$ to 0.60).

($\sim 6.10^{-3}$), a finding which can be easily justified by the microstructure of the material. The strain axis can, again, be divided into several domains:

- for very low ϵ_{\perp} values (domain I), a *non linear* stress-strain relationship is found, immediately followed by a narrow (in the case of the initial preforms) domain of *elastic* behavior (domain II),

- for $\epsilon_{\perp} > \epsilon_{\perp}^e$, a wide domain of *non linear* stress-strain relationship is observed (domain III). This domain corresponds to a microstructural modification of the material, the applied load progressively breaking the pyrocarbon interlayer bridges and bringing closer together the carbon fabric layers. Although this phenomenon must be regarded as an *irreversible microstructural damage*, it results in a very important increase in strength. The stress-strain relationship within this domain - the most important in the case of a non infiltrated preform - is of an exponential type.

- Finally, failure occurs for ϵ_{\perp}^R , within domain IV.

These different domains of strain are still observed for the related 2D-C-C/TiC, their relative widths depending on V_{TiC} , as illustrated in Fig.13 and as already reported for the p-compression tests. It clearly appears from Fig.13 that increasing V_{TiC} results in an important increase in both ϵ_{\perp} (domain II) and σ_{\perp}^R , and in a progressive decrease in ϵ_{\perp}^R . Simultaneously, the widths of domains II and IV increase at the expense of that of domain III.

ϵ_{\perp} increases exponentially with V_{TiC} . A similar relationship is found for σ_{\perp}^R (or σ_{\perp}^e).

3.3 Mechanical anisotropy of the 2D-C-C/TiC

As shown in fig.14, TiC-infiltration progressively reduces the anisotropy of the initial 2D-C-C preform, as V_{TiC} increases. A 2D-C-C/TiC composite fully densified with TiC ($V_{TiC} \sim 0.33$ or 0.44) can be regarded as isotropic as far as the Young modulus is concerned. The effect of TiC-infiltration on the stress to failure is less pronounced since initial preforms do not exhibit a σ^R anisotropy as strong as that reported for E.

3.4 Interlaminar shear tests

Shear tests were performed on two series of 2D-C-C/TiC obtained from different carbon preforms and characterized by increasing values of V_{TiC} . Results of shear tests on composites prepared from a carbon felt ($V_{Po} = 0.73$) were added for the purpose of comparison.

As shown in Fig.15, increasing V_{TiC} significantly raises the shear stress to failure τ^R . However, the nature of the $\tau^R = f(V_{TiC})$ relationship depends on the porosity of the initial preform, as already found in p-compression.

- for composites deriving from rather low V_{Po} preforms, a single linear relationship is observed independent of V_{TiC} ($V_{Po} = 0.29$ preform),

- for composites obtained from high V_{Po} preforms, two different linear relationships are noted on each side of a critical TiC volume fraction ($V_{TiC}^c \sim 0.12$ or 0.23 for composites deriving respectively from 2D-C-C ($V_{Po} = 0.58$) and from a carbon felt ($V_{Po} = 0.73$)). When $V_{TiC} < V_{TiC}^c$, the TiC-infiltration results in a weak increase in τ^R . On the contrary, when $V_{TiC} > V_{TiC}^c$, a much more significant effect is found.

Finally, failure by interlayer delamination disappears when the residual porosity V_p is less than 0.15 whatever V_{Po} , as already noted in p-compression tests, indicating that the interlayer filling is no longer the weakest point of 2D-C-C/TiC when V_p is below ~ 0.15 .

4 - THERMAL EXPANSION

2D-C-C are known to exhibit a marked thermal expansion anisotropy resulting

Due to the 2D-microstructure of the composites, most of the tests were performed on specimens cut, before TiC-infiltration, either parallelly (1) or perpendicularly (2) to the fabric layers, as indicated in fig.7.

3 - MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Compression and interlaminar shear tests were run at room temperature, as a function of V_{TiC} , on 2D-C-C/TiC obtained from preforms characterized by different V_{p0} . The compression tests were performed both parallelly (p-compression) and perpendicularly (o-compression) to the carbon fabric layers, on cylindrical samples ($\phi = 8\text{mm}$; $h = 16\text{mm}$). The interlaminar shear tests were conducted with two types of experimental set ups involving either a couple of samples (20x9x5mm) as identical as possible, or one single specimen (25.4x6.35x6.35mm). In all cases, the test samples were machined before TiC-CVI processing. The strain rates were respectively 0.1mm per minute for the compression tests and 0.5mm per minute for the shear tests.

3.1 Mechanical behavior of 2D-C-C/TiC in p-compression, vs. V_{TiC}

The stress-strain curve is represented, in Fig.8 for one of the porous 2D-C-C initial preforms used to prepare 2D-C-C/TiC. It first appears that the *strain to failure is very small* (i.e. $\sim 6 \cdot 10^{-3}$) due to the rigidity of the carbon fiber fabrics (which are consolidated with pyrocarbon). The strain axis can be divided in three domains:

- for $0 < \epsilon_{//} < \epsilon_{//}^i$ (domain I), a *non linear* stress-strain relationship corresponding to a progressive (but not permanent) rigidification,
- for $\epsilon_{//}^i < \epsilon_{//} < \epsilon_{//}^j$ (domain II), an *elastic* behavior (characterized by a Young modulus $E_{//}$),
- for $\epsilon_{//} > \epsilon_{//}^j$ (domain III), a *pseudo-plastic* behavior, related to a progressive mechanical damage of the material, up to failure for $\epsilon_{//}^R$.

These three domains of strain are also observed for the related 2D-C-C/TiC, their relative widths depending on the amount of TiC, as illustrated in fig.9. Increasing V_{TiC} strongly raises both $E_{//}$ and $\sigma_{//}^R$. Furthermore, $\epsilon_{//}^R$ first decreases as V_{TiC} increases, undergoes a minimum (that depends on V_{p0}) and finally increases with V_{TiC} . This minimum was found to occur for a residual porosity V_p , related to both V_{TiC} and V_{p0} by equation (3) of the order of $V_p = 0.15$. For $V_p > 0.15$, failure occurs by interlayer delamination, the too porous C/TiC hybrid matrix still remaining the weakest part of the material. On the contrary, for $V_p < 0.15$, a translayer failure is observed showing that the interlayer C/TiC filling is strong enough to prevent delamination.

The variations of both $E_{//}$ and $\sigma_{//}^R$ vs. V_{TiC} , are represented in fig.10 and 11 for composites prepared from different preforms. In the case of 2D-C-C/TiC derived from a preform of *rather limited open porosity* ($V_{p0} = 0.26-0.35$), *linear relationships* are found between $E_{//}$ (or $\sigma_{//}^R$) and V_{TiC} whatever V_{TiC} . On the contrary, in the case of 2D-C-C/TiC derived from a preform of *high initial porosity*, two domains of V_{TiC} must be considered, on each side of a critical TiC volume fraction V_{TiC}^C (with $V_{TiC}^C \sim 0.12-0.15$):

- for $V_{TiC} < V_{TiC}^C$, TiC-infiltration does not result in any significant increase in either $E_{//}$ or $\sigma_{//}^R$. Therefore, it will be called *inactive infiltration*,
- for $V_{TiC} > V_{TiC}^C$, both $E_{//}$ and $\sigma_{//}^R$ strongly increase with V_{TiC} , according to linear relationships similar to those reported above for composites prepared from low V_{p0} preforms. This TiC-infiltration will be referred to as *active infiltration*. It is believed that it corresponds to the occurrence of TiC deposits thick enough to form strong *bridges* between adjacent carbon fabric layers.

3.2 Mechanical behavior of 2D-C-C/TiC in o-compression, vs V_{TiC}

The stress-strain relationship derived from an o-compression test performed on a porous 2D-C-C preform is represented in fig.12. It appears that the *strain to failure ϵ_{\perp}^R is much higher* ($\sim 300 \cdot 10^{-3}$) than that observed in p-compression

from their microstructure and from the thermal expansion properties of carbon itself. Since it has been reported earlier that replacing the C matrix by SiC strongly decreases their thermal expansion, thermal expansion tests were conducted in an argon atmosphere and up to 2000°C, on 2D-C-C/TiC, as a function of V_{TiC} in both the p- and o-directions [4,10].

The variation of the thermal expansion $\Delta l/l_0$ of 2D-C-C/TiC composites vs V_{TiC} is shown in Fig.16. The thermal expansion progressively increases with V_{TiC} in the p-direction (Fig.16a). On the contrary, for the o-direction, it first increases with V_{TiC} (up to about $V_{TiC} = 0.10-0.15$) then remains constant when V_{TiC} is further increased up to $V_{TiC} \sim V_{P_0}$ (Fig.16b).

As shown in fig.17, the thermal expansion coefficient anisotropy, $\alpha_l/\alpha_{\parallel}$, decreases with increasing V_{TiC} , this effect being less pronounced at high temperature than at low temperature. We conclude then that TiC-infiltration of porous 2D-C-C lowers indeed their thermal expansion anisotropy, as already observed for the related 2D-C-C/SiC [4-10].

5 - RESISTANCE TOWARDS OXIDATION

For the purpose of comparison, and having in mind the fact that the oxidation resistance of TiC is intermediate between that of carbon and SiC, oxidation tests were performed on 2D-C-C/TiC (samples of type (1): $\phi = 8\text{mm}$; $h = 8\text{mm}$). The tests were conducted in air ($D = 1.5$ to 8l per hour), the sample weight variations being recorded vs. time.

The oxidation rate depends on temperature, oxygen partial pressure, gas flow rate, residual open porosity and time. As illustrated in fig. 18, the air oxidation of fully TiC densified samples ($V_{TiC} = 0.32$, almost no residual porosity) is very weak up to about 900°C. The observed weight increase (less than 2% after 7 hours) is due to the oxidation of TiC to rutile that progressively coats the sample. At higher temperatures, the weight increase period is followed by a weight loss probably related to an in-depth diffusion of oxygen resulting in an oxidation of the carbon preform. Expected, therefore, the TiO_2 layer is not protective in opposition to that of SiO_2 in the case of SiC-matrix composites [4,10].

For a given material, the higher T and p_{O_2} the faster the transition from the first to the second oxidation mechanism, as illustrated in fig.19,20. Moreover, the oxidation behavior strongly depends on the material microstructure (V_{TiC}, V_p). With increasing V_{TiC} (and, thus, decreasing V_p), the transition from weight increase to weight loss oxidation mechanism requires more and more time, at a given temperature and p_{O_2} . On the other hand, the rate of formation of TiO_2 on one hand and that of carbon oxides on the other remains approximately constant whatever V_{TiC} (Fig.20).

The in-depth oxidation of carbon observed at high temperature is probably favored by the existence of microcracks within the TiC-matrix as already mentioned (Fig.5).

It thus appears that 2D-C-C/TiC composites, although they do not exhibit the outstanding oxidation resistance of the related 2D-C-C/SiC materials, have, nevertheless, a better behavior in oxidizing atmosphere than the parent 2D-C-C composites. They also have a higher thermal stability than the 2D-C-C/SiC.

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Fig.1: CVD-phase diagram of titanium carbide ($\text{CH}_4\text{-TiCl}_4\text{-H}_2$ gas mixtures)

Fig.2: Variation of the thermodynamic yields as a function of the initial composition in $\text{TiCl}_4\text{-CH}_4\text{-H}_2$

Fig.3:CVI chamber used for the synthesis of 2D-C-C/TiC composites

Fig.4:Weight increase vs time during the synthesis of 2D-C-C/TiC

Fig.5:Microstructure of 2D-C-C/TiC composites from PAN-based carbon preforms: (a) $V_{TiC} = 0.20$, (b) almost fully TiC-densified

Fig.6:Evolution of porosity during TiC-infiltration of 2D-C-C preforms

Fig.7:Orientation of the carbon cloth layers in the samples used for mechanical and physical tests

Fig.8: Stress-strain curve for a 2D-C-C preform loaded in p-compression

Fig.9: Stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/TiC composites loaded in p-compression

Fig.10: Variation of $E_{//}$ vs. V_{TiC} for 2D-C-C/TiC

Fig.11: Variation of $\sigma_{R//}$ vs. V_{TiC} for 2D-C-C/TiC

Fig.12: Stress-strain curve for a 2D-C-C preform loaded in o-compression

Fig.13: Stress-strain curves for 2D-C-C/TiC composites loaded in o-compression

Fig. 14: Variation of the Young modulus anisotropy of 2D-C-C/TiC composites vs. V_{TiC}

Fig. 15: Variation of T_R vs. V_{TiC} for different C-TiC composites

(a)

(b)

Fig. 16: thermal expansion of 2D-C-C/TiC composites vs. V_{TiC} : (a) in p-direction, (b) in o-direction

Fig. 17: Variation of the thermal expansion coefficient anisotropy vs V_{TiC} for 2D-C-C/TiC

Fig. 18: Oxidation kinetics in air of 2D-C-C/TiC (PAN-based fibers) at different T

Fig.19:Oxidation kinetics of 2D-C-C/TiC (PAN-based fibers) at different p_{O_2}

Fig.20:Oxidation kinetics in air of 2D-C-C/TiC (PAN-based fibers) at different V_{TiC}

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